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Research Article

Voices from Foreign Land: A Study of Select Diaspora Narratives of Rohinton Mistry

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ABSTRACT

Diaspora is a social formation outside the nation of its origin. Diaspora deals with the uprooting, forced or voluntary, of the mass of people from their native 'homeland' and their 're-rooting' in the foreign land. The word 'diaspora' comes from the Greek composite verb diasperiein-dia (meaning 'through or across') and speirein (meaning to sow/scatter). Diaspora means to scatter through/across, an act of dispersion or scattering. It is an act of gathering and settlement from the homeland to the host land, which is known as the new land. The term diaspora was not in circulation before the 1980s, and there was no evidence of diaspora theory before that decade. Rohinton Mistry is a writer of the Indian diaspora who settled in a foreign land and speaks about his diasporic consciousness of his homeland through his novels set in Canada. The main objective of the research article is to reveal voices from the cross-border using diasporic narratives in the novels of Rohinton Mistry.

KEYWORDS: uprooting, re-rooting, homeland, foreign land

FULL PAPER**Introduction**

The literary concept of Diaspora is structured with theoretical dimensions and analysis. Diaspora initiated its journey in the 1980s with Gabriel Sheffer's book *Modern Diasporas in International Politics* (1986). Today, the term diaspora studies has emerged as a branch of critical inquiry into the different aspects of people who migrate across national borders. The movement of diaspora was aided and encouraged by new economic pressures, political upheavals, personal and community aspirations for upward mobility, and innovations in science and technology. It is a fundamental phenomenon involving the uprooting, forced or voluntary, of people from their homeland and their 're-rooting' in a new homeland. Diaspora writers have a strong nostalgia for the land they left behind and its culture(s), but at the same time, they try to assimilate into the dominant culture of the new space. Each diaspora writer has their own socio-political, cultural, and economic dimensions reflected in their literary works. We often encounter the term 'internal diaspora' to refer to movements within the country. The people who leave their native place because of social, political, cultural, religious, untouchability, violence, and other issues. They began traveling to another part of the same country. It is apt to use diaspora or diasporic terms to describe them. If people are migrating within a country or state due to social and economic insecurity, it is called 'internal migration'. When people migrate from one place to another, it is referred to as 'external diaspora'. Diaspora is divided into two types: the old and the new diaspora. The term 'old diaspora' refers to the legal migration of labour to a foreign land for economic purposes. The new diaspora advocates voluntary migration by Indian writers or others to a foreign land to secure a bright future. These writers became more creative after their settlement in a foreign land.

Rohinton Mistry is one of the leading diaspora writers of the twentieth (20th) century in Indian English Literature. As a diaspora writer, he consistently explores his homeland (India) through his fiction, even though he lives in Canada (a foreign land). He is often compared with Charles Dickens for presenting social, political, and cultural realities through an artistic amalgamation of city and rural life, reflected in his novels. In his novels, we come across a fascinating account of the Parsi community, which lives especially in Bombay (hereinafter referred to as Mumbai in this research paper). Memory plays a vital role in his fiction. Mumbai plays a larger role in his novels. While writing these three novels, he effectively used his memory and imagination to shape the social, political, and cultural events of his time in India.

Such a Long Journey (1991):

Rohinton Mistry's *Such a Long Journey* (1991) is set against the backdrop of the India-Pakistan war and the birth of Bangladesh. Mistry's novel centers on the Parsi

community and the historic war between India and Pakistan. Walker Connor defines diaspora as the condition of displaced people who retain a collective memory, vision, or myth of their original homeland, its physical location, history, and achievements (Lahiri 10). The texture of the novel is interwoven in diasporic consciousness. Mistry's obsession with his homeland (India) is reflected in the novel. He has tried to deconstruct and repossess his past using nostalgia. The nostalgia, or feeling of homesickness, derives from the Homeric term 'nostos', which means 'homecoming'. Mistry has employed nostalgia to discuss past events in the life of his mouthpiece character, Gustad Noble. Subsequently, the feeling of pleasure and pain of the Parsis is described in the text. Nostalgia often surfaces in the text as the novel's hero reminisces about his family and the country's socio-political and cultural turmoil. The nostalgia helps bring the novelist's old memories to the fore by narrating a story with the same meaning. Mistry became nostalgic while remembering the same places located in Mumbai. The nostalgia is based on creative imagination, becoming a formalist practice unrelated to social conditions.

The text is the novelist's attempt to deconstruct and rejuvenate the past during his stay in India. Mumbai is represented as a microcosm of the world in his fictional works. The journey of the city has initiated towards fundamentalism and the narrow-mindedness of the people about their beliefs in religious and communal fanaticism. Gustad Noble is determined to fulfill his dreams, but he encounters obstacles and hardships along the way. Gustad's journey is marked by themes of alienation and powerlessness in the chaotic city.

The Parsis are an ethno-religious minority in India. Ethnicity comes from the Greek word 'ethnos' (meaning 'nation'). It is based on the context of the settlement of immigrant groups arriving from outside the nation or state. The Parsis are mostly settled in Mumbai and Gujarat during the seventh (7th) century. Ethnicity reveals a community based on shared cultural and national features that distinguishes minorities from mainstream communities. Ethnically, Parsis differ from the mainstream Hindu community or other ethnic groups living in Mumbai. Ethnicity is traced to the nation-state/homeland from which the diaspora emigrates. Parsis are an ethnic community with a cultural heritage comprising myths, beliefs, values, and practices. In a multicultural nation/state (India/Maharashtra), ethnicity is generally associated with a minority to show marginalization from the mainstream of society.

Such a Long Journey shows that Parsis are a lost bastion of the city that has a mixed heritage. The text's political background helps study Indian politics through the author's diasporic perspectives. The population of Parsis is decreasing day by day due to internal problems like late marriages, low fertility, migration, leading a celibate life, and the exclusion of children born to women married to non-Parsis, etc. As per the many estimates, there are hardly one million Parsis left throughout the world. It is

noteworthy to quote Aditi Kapoor, who expresses the concern for diminishing Parsi community: "Unless something is done to augment their fast depleting numbers and to review their religion, the Parsis after an illustrious past could well just fade out in oblivion" (Kapadiya 162). The novel not only focuses on the Parsi diaspora in the Indian context but also projects its anti-colonial resistance. Mistry typically specifies that Parsis are an ethno-religious minority community in his novel. It is important to quote V.L.V.N. Narendra Kumar, who says, 'The Parsees are attempting to assert their ethnic identity in diverse ways. The Parsee English novel reflects the Parsi community's assertion (Dodiya 44).

Rohinton Mistry, as a diaspora writer, left his homeland (India) and settled in a foreign land (Canada). Diaspora writers express a sense of belonging through their literary works when they emigrate from one country to another. Firstly, he/she finds that the geographical conditions differ from those in his/her country or native place. Then he or she comes across problems of language, culture, tradition, lifestyle, and sensibility that differ from those of his/her native land. Certain things have to be adjusted in a foreign or migrated land, and one has to cope with the local, social, and political milieu of the new land. Mistry revealed his belongingness by reading the daily newspaper, listening to news about his homeland on the radio, and watching it on television. He also shows his belonging to the native land by visiting his relatives, neighbours, and friends who live in an apartment in Mumbai.

Rohinton Mistry conveys religious equilibrium and cultural relativism through an artistic portrayal of the pavement artist on the compound wall of the Khodadad building. The painting of God and Goddesses symbolizes that all religions are equal and that religion is culturally relative. The compound wall gives a sense of security and protection from external calamities. Gustad describes a compound wall as:

"Sole provider of privacy, especially for Jimmy and Gustad when they did their 'Kustis' at dawn. Over six feet high, the wall ran the length of the compound, sheltering them from non-Parsis while they prayed with the glow spreading in the east". (SLJ 32)

In this connection, it is noteworthy to quote Nilufer Bharucha, who voices similarly: "The wall both includes and excludes. It is both protective and reductive. It protects the Parsi community from the ingress of the engulfing Indian world. However, it also makes this world isolationist" (Bharucha 123). Earlier, the compound wall was used as a public urinal, which spread mosquitoes in the Khodadad building. The passers-by polluted it. Noble invited the pavement artist to use the compound wall as a canvas for his murals depicting various Indian gods and goddesses. The compound wall of Khodadad's building miraculously turns into a shrine of races and religions, as "A stinking, filthy disgrace has become a beautiful, fragrant place which makes everyone

feel good” (SLJ 189). It is worthwhile to quote Anjana Desai, who says, ‘It, thus, becomes a multi-religious shrine...symbolizing the accommodative and assimilative spirit of Parsis, not numerically strong enough for a militant assertion of identity’ (Desai 134). Parsis assert their identity authentically by referring to others’ faith. Mistry has preserved ‘self-respect of his communities’ by publicly worshipping the Parsi religion. As a diasporic writer, he is not aggressive against any religion. Vice versa, he discusses cultural materialism by displaying paintings of Gods and Goddesses from different religions on the compound wall.

A Fine Balance (1995):

Rohinton Mistry’s second novel, *A Fine Balance*, is an epic book. As a diaspora writer, Mistry is obsessed with his homeland, seeking to reconstruct the social, historical, political, and cultural atmosphere of India through his imagination and reality. The text is dedicated to his beloved wife, Freny. The text is to be read as an expression of subaltern voices, caste and class oppression, the citizen, and the nation. The novel is set in an unidentified city during the most infamous internal emergency proclaimed by Indira Gandhi, the then Prime Minister of India. Mistry has discussed the anguish and anxiety of the untouchables and minority people of the country who suffered a lot during the infamous emergency. It is worthwhile to quote K.C. Belliappa in this regard, who says, “the narrative voice in Mistry’s fictional discourse achieves ‘a fine balance’ between involvement and detachment, thus providing a reliable witness to an eventful era in the nation’s history” (Kadam 181).

A Fine Balance is not only centered on Parsis but also captures the scathing social reality of the chamar community in a village. It is significant to quote Mistry’s interview: ‘I made a conscious decision in this book to include more than this, mainly because in India seventy-five percent of Indians live in villages and I wanted to embrace more of the social reality of India’ (Morey 95). He expressed his agony with the chamar community as an untouchable in the Hindu majority, who are marginalized due to their lower caste. He tries to maintain a fine balance between ‘exploiters and exploited’ in the novel. The text proves to be a platform for a friendly atmosphere among minorities like Untouchables, Parsis, Muslims, and Sikhs. Thakur Dharmasi’s dominance subjugates the chamar community. Caste discrimination is highlighted in the text. The novel focuses on subaltern encounters of lower caste people by drawing attention to society.

Nostalgia is a key element of diaspora in the text. Mistry uses a nonlinear narrative structure, allowing him to move easily between the past and the present. He artistically narrates the story of four characters. These characters are totally unaware of the historical emergency proclaimed in India. These characters became victims of this internal emergency. During the emergency, the question arose in the minds of

minorities and others: where did they belong? It raises questions about their identity. He uses flashbacks and nostalgia to describe past events in these characters' lives. Dina Dalal, the protagonist of the novel, recalled past events through nostalgia. She remembered the memory of her married life and talked about Indian culture and tradition by following 'One Wife! One Husband! Dina Dalal recalled her childhood days through nostalgia.

Rohinton Mistry's *A Fine Balance* is not only a work of fiction but also a tragedy about minorities living in India. The text deals less with the struggle, anguish, anxiety, and insecurity of Parsis living in India but more with the exploitation of untouchables. It presents quotidian life among Parsis, Dalits, and Muslims, capturing diverse social issues across the metropolitan city and rural areas. The Parsis are an ethno-religious minority community living in India. The minorities and others were going through anxiety and insecurity during the period of internal emergency created by the people in power. This emergency had created socio-political and cultural chaos. It affects the lives of minorities and downtrodden people in the country. They are struggling with the cultural aloofness of the majoritarian community living in India.

The novel encounters minorities' anxiety, feelings of isolation, homelessness, belongingness, and fear during the period of Emergency in India, where minorities are not secure in the hands of majoritarians. The novel narrates the inner feelings of Parsis, Sikhs, Muslims, and Chamars who are alienated from the mainstream of society. These minorities were exploited under the power of the then government. Mistry reinterprets community as an outcome of globalization, in which it refers to the challenging of structures, boundaries, values, and practices of traditional communities. It brings individuals like Dina Dalal, Maneck Kohlah, Ishvar, and Omprakash in contact with one another. It is apt to quote Anderson:

Both human mobility and the growth of communication networks reduce geography's predominance as a force in shaping communities. It is still an important fact, but many communities are much more fluid, and some are placeless. (Roy & Pillai 182)

In the era of globalization, the source of community has changed to a global community. The word community connotes a group of people who come together under one roof to fulfil their needs within typical social boundaries.

The characters' memories were permanent in Mistry's novel, revealing the importance of individual and cultural identity. It is important to quote Mistry's interview with Angela Lambert: "Mistry said that he had met his wife Freny Elavia at a music school where she was taking voice and piano lessons, and I was doing classes in music Theory and composition" (Bharucha 151).

Family Matters (2000):

Rohinton Mistry's third novel, *Family Matters*, is the most acclaimed literary masterpiece in Indian English Literature. He returns to the Parsi community like his first novel, *Such a Long Journey*. The text is set against the backdrop of the Babri Mosque demolition in Ayodhya on 6 December 1992. It creates communal violence between Hindus and Muslims. Hindus claim that the site on which the mosque was built is the birthplace of Lord Ram. Therefore, it was a pious place for their religion. It is set against the backdrop of communalist politics and corruption in Mistry's last novel, *Family Matters*. Shiv Sena has captured the plot of the novel, as in the earlier novel *Such a Long Journey*. The author narrated the Hindu ideology of Shiv Sena in the text. Rohinton Mistry has expressed the reality and agony of Mumbai in *Family Matters*."

That is how people have lived in Bombay. That is why Bombay has survived floods, disease, plague, water shortage, bursting drains and sewers, and all the population pressures. In her heart, there is room for everyone who wants to make a home here. (FM 136).

He has raised several burning issues, including flooding, disease, plague, water shortages, bursting drains, and sewer problems in Mumbai. All these issues arise only because of the city's overpopulation. It is haunted so badly to highlight the city's gloomy, pessimistic nature. Mistry conveys the city's universal nature, making it a refuge for homeless people in Mumbai. Minorities and others reflected in the text were alienated from mainstream Hindu society due to cultural diversity and multiculturalism. The minorities and others were feeling a sense of loss, insecurity, fragmentation, anxiety, and fear in a dominated Hindu society after the post-Babri Mosque riots.

Rohinton Mistry uses nostalgia to narrate past events in his life through italic passages in the text. Nariman Vakeel, the protagonist of the novel, lost his memories due to Parkinson's disease. He expresses inner and outer experiences using nostalgia and flashback techniques. He became nostalgic when he recalled the love story with Lucy. The author's immigration story is narrated through the mouthpiece character, Yezad Chenoy. The Parsis were immigrating to the foreign land for economic and security purposes. It is apt to quote V. L. V. N. Narendrakumar:

The Parsees prefer the West since it offers unlimited scope for growth and prosperity. Dislocation is part of the Parsee psyche. Exiled twelve hundred years ago, they came to India. Now they are migrating to the west in search of greener pastures. Thus, there is 'double migration' in the case of Parsees. (Dodiya 84)

Yezad is under stress due to domestic problems, quotidian work, overcrowded trains, inadequate salaries, and an uncondusive atmosphere in India. Seeing the social,

political, and cultural chaos in the country, he was eager to immigrate to Canada. He applied to the Canadian High Commission, New Delhi. He wrote a letter to the Canadian Supreme Court about their inspiring geography, people, places, and the very generous policy of multiculturalism. This policy never demands discarding the old culture before letting them share in a new one. Mr. Mazobashi, an immigrant officer, interviewed with Yezad. He behaved rudely toward the Chenoy family and asked them questions in an insulting manner, making them feel inferior.

The term 'identity' is primarily associated with a sense of belonging in the new sociological arena. Postmodern thinkers encourage the term 'identity' to change the nature of socio-political, cultural, and personal identities in society. It is necessary to understand the personal form of identity, which comprises what an individual feels about their identity. The impact of their self-identity is on their social and personal behaviours in society. Secondly, the individual's identity should be understood in terms of the influence of cultural life on identity. In the world of globalization, social, personal, and cultural identities are more fluid and less rigid. People are free to make a broader range of choices to establish their own identity. They are not tied to the country's socio-political and cultural identity. They can create their new identity through highly individualized forms.

The religious components of identity are important in the text. Mistry has raised a question on the Parsi identity when Jehangir asked his father, "Daddy, can I change my name to John? As a short form of Jehangir. Did you hear that, Roxie? Your son wants to become a Christian" (FM 214). Roxana has explained to Jehangir the religious identity, "Listen, Jehangla, your Christian friends have Christian names. Your Hindu friends have Hindu names. You are a Parsi, so you have a Persian name. Be proud of it, religious identity is not thrown like an old shoe" (FM 214). Roxana sticks to her religious identity in an orthodox manner because she grew up in the Paris culture.

Nariman was discharged from the Parsi General Hospital. He continues to live with his stepchildren, Coomy and Jal. Coomy was reluctant to perform her responsibilities to attend to him as a dependent. Nariman leads in the state of unbelonging and homelessness, even though he himself purchased a seven-room flat in Chateau Felicity after his retirement. He hands over the flat in the name of his stepchildren, Coomy and Jal. Mistry raised questions on the personal identity of Nariman Vakeel when feelings of belongingness, unbelongingness, and homelessness arose in his mind after Coomy's vicious plan to send her bedridden father to her half-sister, Roxana.

Mistry's description of the memory and the plasticity of remembering multiple events that have already happened in the past. It proves with his memory to creative insertion than accurate preservation finds remarkable resonance as Eric Kondel states

in his book memory as; 'when people try to recollect a story, for example sometimes they make creative errors, detecting some part of the story, fabricating other parts and generally trying to reconstruct the information in a way that makes sense' (Parui 41). Mistry is a postmodern writer who deploys the motif of time to underscore the entanglement of the private and historical memory in *Family Matters*. Mistry describes Coomy as being forced to recall memories of her biological father and mother, who consider her stepfather responsible for the death of her mother.

Conclusion:

The research article presents the foreign voice of a diaspora writer from a foreign land through his fictional works. He uses diasporic narratives like nostalgia, identity, insecurity, anxiety, and anguish of minorities, homelessness and belongingness, multiculturalism, ethnicity, and alienation, which are very persistent and occur in his novels. These diasporic narratives are the key indicators of understanding anxiety and insecurities of diaspora writers through Indian English Literature.

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